

Importance of Education in the Novels of Manju Kapur

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Abstract:

This research article delves into the thematic importance of education in the novels of Manju Kapur, a prominent contemporary Indian author. Kapur's literary oeuvre, including works such as *Difficult Daughters*, *A Married Woman*, and *The Immigrant*, portrays a nuanced and compelling exploration of the role of education in shaping the lives and identities of her characters. The study employs a comprehensive analysis of Kapur's narrative techniques, character development, and socio-cultural contexts to unravel the multifaceted ways in which education acts as a transformative force in her storytelling.

The article begins by situating Kapur's works within the broader landscape of postcolonial literature, emphasizing the intersectionality of gender, class, and education in the lives of her protagonists. It subsequently scrutinizes the evolving societal norms and educational opportunities presented in Kapur's novels, shedding light on the characters' struggles, aspirations, and personal growth within the educational framework. Additionally, the research investigates the impact of education on the characters' relationships, societal roles, and the negotiation of traditional and modern values.

Drawing on literary theory and cultural studies, this article contributes to the ongoing discourse on the representation of education in literature, particularly within the context of South Asian women's experiences. Through a close reading of Kapur's novels, the research seeks to provide valuable insights into the intricate ways in which education serves as a catalyst for empowerment, self-discovery, and societal transformation in the narratives crafted by Manju Kapur. This exploration not only enriches our understanding of Kapur's literary contributions but also adds depth to the broader conversations surrounding the pivotal role of education in shaping individual destinies and societal structures.

Keywords: Education, Feminism, Patriarchy, Modern woman, Gender Discrimination.

Introduction

Education is a concise declaration and it serves as a tool to cultivate an individual's existence. Education is unequivocally the most crucial tool to transform an individual's life. Education for a young individual commences within the confines of their own household. The circle of life process continues until the end of our lives. Education unequivocally reveals the significance of an individual's existence. Education enhances one's intellectual capacity, skills, and fosters charm and mental perspective. One of the most notable aspects is that education provides the human race with options for employment. A well educated individual is likely to secure a prestigious employment opportunity. Education plays a significant part in our culture. While some individuals possess this knowledge, others are hindered from providing their children with adequate education due to many factors. Manju Kapur's works eloquently highlight the significance of education in our culture. Manju Kapur is a renowned author in the field of Indian English literature. She has explored a range of topics in her works, including Education. Manju Kapur gained widespread recognition in 1998 with the publication of her debut novel, *Difficult Daughters*. The work received the esteemed Commonwealth Eurasia Region Award for the best debut novel in 1999. Subsequently, she presented *The Immigrant* (2008), *Home* (2005), and *Custody* (2011). She portrays the lady as a figure who combats her own education, freedom, and married life. Her writings explore the dynamics between men and women, the human urge for connection, the yearning for fulfilment, gender discrimination, the marginalisation of women, and the struggle against injustice and suffering. The novels also analyse the diverse repercussions on our society. The female protagonists in her stories are portrayed as characters with limited intelligence but exceptional abilities. They are assertive, skilled, introverted nonconformists driven to embody the ideals of contemporary femininity. This paper examines the significance and worth of education, particularly for women, in both personal and societal contexts, with a specific emphasis on the novels of Manju Kapur.

Education Allays Pauperism

Education plays a significant part in our culture. While some individuals are aware of this and actively encourage their children to pursue education, there are many others who are unable to provide their children with a suitable education. During ancient times, women faced barriers to education. However, a few women persevered and obtained an education, not only for themselves but also for future generations. There is a saying that states that when a boy receives an education, he is able to utilise it for his own benefit. When a girl receives her education, the entire family will benefit. In this theme, Manju Kapur also emphasised the significance of education, not only for women but for the entire society as well. She places a significantly greater emphasis on education in her works. Manju Kapur is widely regarded as the foremost modern Indian English women novelist, highly esteemed for her work. The individual in question has written four highly regarded novels, namely *Difficult Daughters*, *A Married Woman*, *Home*, *Immigrant*, and *Brothers*. *Difficult Daughters* was the recipient of the commonwealth writer's prize in 1998, while *Home* was a

finalist for the Hutch Crossword Book Award in 2006. Kapur skillfully constructs the familial background in all of her stories. In an interview with jai Arjun, Manju Kapur says:

“Literature by women about families, always has these larger considerations, with years of studying texts, it becomes almost second nature to look beneath the surface at social and economic forces, gender relationships and how they are played out in an arena that in my writing happens to be the home”. (Singh)

She portrayed her characters through powerful educationalist, strong and well talented humans. Often she insists in her novels that education alleviates the poverty of the society. In *Difficult Daughters* she gave much more importance to education. Her heroine “Virmati” loves to study. She was admired naturally towards Sakuntala her nephew because of her studies. Sakuntala stand by her own to finish her higher studies though their family scold her a lot she achieved it. Since her childhood Virmati used to do her household and read after that. She was admired towards the professor because of his slang and the knowledge of literature. Though Kasturi the mother of Virmati banned her to study higher studies she passed her FA Exam. Kapur gives a shade of Swarnalatha a friend of Virmati, when she started to join in the politics in the pre independence period. Education is powerful and through that we can stand in our life independently. This was believed by the professor and after getting married also he make Virmati to learn her further studies.

Education Vs. Marriage

Our society by nature is based on patriarchy and women were not permit to make money to support living. Additionally they did not acquire the right to possess property and were completely be in control on men. They were created defenseless, and often come up against a situation of discrimination and maltreatment. But everything can remove if women start to go schools and colleges. They acquire the knowledge to know their rights for freedom and struggle and have to fight for justice. In *Difficult daughters* there was always an endless argument between “*Education verses Marriage*”. The words of Virmati not be heard by anyone. When virmati wished to give practice to her English, her mother Kasturi’s only aim is to take care of the children and doing house hold duties. Kasturi needs virmati to learn all the household duties for her future life.

“May be here was the club to her unhappiness. It was useless looking for answers inside the home. One had to look outside. To education, freedom and the bright lights of Lahore colleges” (DD-15)

When she protested and started to study the between hers and the professor, she compares her fiancé and she rejected Inderjeet and also she said to her mother.

“Let Indumati marry. Give her the khes you are making. I don’t want any bedding, pots and pans nothing.”(DD-55)

“My mother, my masi, all studied. It is the rivaz in our family. Even now my father keeps getting my mother books and magazines to read”. (DD.36)

In some families the tradition permit to provide the basic education but not the higher education. Women were not allowed to go to job also. Manju Kapur’s *Home* visualizes whether a girl in a family get education or not it should finally ends in her marriage. When a girl started to get her education whether she wish or not it should complete or quit in her marriage. In Kapur’s home Sona steps out of the education system when she was arranged with a bride from Banwari lal’s family in Karol Bagh,

“Will sona, from an educated family, be happy with shopkeepers? The boy is only high school pass, but sona now says she does not want to study anymore, she wants to remain on the same level as her husband”(Home 8)

Her sister Rupa finished her B.A. then no more marriage proposal came to stop her education. After her completion of education her father started to find out her a best life partner, which was his friend’s son. Then came to Nisha’s education the next generation started to see each and every pros and cons for a best school. They also search and consider the distance of school which suits to Nisha . Kapur showed here the gender bias of the society who give importance to girl’s education and distance also matter. When Nisha joined school and came with flying colours she was appreciated and praised by the family.

At the age of ten, she had limitations in both her household and educational environment. The mother began preparing her daughter for all eventualities. Regarding Raju, Sona expressed concern about his academic progress due to his lack of aptitude for studies and mischievous behaviour towards Nisha. He achieved the minimum passing grades in his 10th class. Kapur observes the societal prioritisation of males and the marginalisation of girls. As Nisha matured, her college courses initially progressed favourably for a few days. Nisha's devotion to Suresh hindered her ability to focus on her academic pursuits. The percentage is declining and attendance is insufficient. Consequently, she was prohibited from taking the examination. Her family members receive updates regarding her romantic relationships. Now her romantic involvement with Suresh is revealed. Nisha must meticulously scrutinise each word at home. Feeling shattered and disheartened, she succumbs to the familial pressure to acquiesce to a man selected by her family. One of her family members had numerous marriage proposals, but none of them resulted in a settled marriage. She requests a solitary year from her father to demonstrate her competence.

“Give me a chance to show you what I can do” (Home-287)

From this point she starts as a successful business woman. Her father also supported her and suggested a name for her shop - “Nisha Creations”. There she started to shine in her career and starts responding to the issue of marriage with Arvind.

Education Reduces Prejudices in Society

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Kapur's *The Immigrant* (2008) is an effective novel which focuses education can reduce prejudices in society. Nina is a lecturer of English in Miranda college. Nina's mother arranged a suitable guy for her and she always worried about her future only though she was an army man's wife she worried about Nina's future. After getting married she too feels about her education and wants to continue that. Her husband allows her to study a librarian course which should be useful for her. Before that Nina loves to read books and it is her passion and hobby. After her marriage she needs the company of books than her husband even in night times. In her university when she started to go she admired the education system and she decides to switch over to it. In foreign countries if we want to work, as per the rule to complete a diploma or degree course in that country. So Nina decides to study librarian course with the permission of her husband.

Kapur here initializes the courage of a woman who stands herself in a foreign country not because of her husband but with the education and the job. Kapur's *Custody* a novel which shows the education is the powerful weapon in the society. In the novel though it deals with emotional break-up of a parent, it also emphasizes the education as a powerful weapon. Ashok Khanna, Raman's boss loved Shagun and the family break-up starts. Though the theme revolves round the parent's divorce and separation, Kapur maintains the education of the children separately and through the characters she visualizes how education must to children. Arjun refuses to go to school, because of his parent and the criticism made by his classmates, shagun and Ashok Khanna want to change his school survival free and peaceful.

They put him DPA (Dehradun Public Academy) with a great risk. After years passed Arjun made himself realizes the importance of education in life and he concentrated in his studies than his family issues. On the other side Ishita was denied by her husband because she was unable to conceive. When she came to her mother's home she decides to study a Master degree in history to stand up her position. Here Kapur emphasizing that education only protect our women to be confident person. In Kapur's 'Brothers' she too emphasis the theme of education when Tapti Giana wants to finish his degree, marriage interferes.

She does not want to quit it so she finished her studies and married Mangal who is the brother of CM Himmat Singh Gaina. Tapti's mother advised her to finish her degree and try to attend her competitive exams. Tapti aims to become an officer in government sectors. She is good in her studies and has secured gold medals from the university. After her marriage she was committed with all her household duties and giving birth to a child. Though Mangal Singh Giana treated her as a queen in his home, he refuses her to go outside. Though they had a daughter as a first child, she conceived again within a few months and delivered again a girl baby.

Mangal hesitated to see that but he needs a male baby for his heir. So often he force Tapti to give a boy baby. Though Tapti was strongly advised and warned by her family doctor not to conceive again, because of her health condition, Mangal hesitate to hear those words. Tapti's mother often advises her to continue her studies and write exams as her aim. She worried for missing her studies. When her husband seems to be struggling with his

cement factory he needs her support also. At that time she told him that she wants to go for coaching classes for competitive exams. He denied it and he force her to take care of the family only. At last with a great effort she passed her Probation Officer Grade I exams pride filled Mangal.

“His wife knew what it cost him to say this how little he had wanted her to have her own career and how certain he must have been that she would fail” (Brothers 274)

Through all her novels Kapur handled the theme of education by her protagonist and other characters. She has given a reality that education brings always dignity, honour and power. Though all are educating themselves, the development of society and the nation based on the education of men and women.

“I do not wish them (women) to have power over men, but over themselves”. (81)

To Conclude

We are adapting to a new world that is inundated with both modern and classic standards. However, occasionally our innate reliance can devastate an individual's existence. For instance, a select few individuals are inherently destined for unfortunate circumstances from the moment they are born. We have even classified certain individuals as untouchables and denied them their inherent rights from birth. This theme is evident in all of Manju Kapur's stories, as ignorant ladies place their reliance solely in miraculous interventions from above. Kapur believes that these women in society are losing their valuable time and earning potential by listening to the beliefs and norms of the patriarchy. As a result, they are just living in a state of darkness. Kapur advocates for the education committee that supports women's education. She asserts that there are numerous individuals who exploit the lack of knowledge among these uneducated women. She asserts that education enhances their social standing and personal well-being. I give data to support the assertion that education serves as an illuminating force in times of adversity, offering a promising path towards a better quality of life.

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